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Abstract. Colm Tóibín is one of the most prominent literary voices in Ireland today, but he had to face enormous difficulties in having his first novel, *The South* (1990), published. In this article, I will look at the 1986 manuscript of the novel—on file in the National Library of Ireland—and argue that after all his revisions, Tóibín softened the protagonist’s characterization as an “abject” mother and sanitized the language of her sexual feelings. Central to this essay will be the idea that when Tóibín wrote *The South* in the 1980s, the expression of sexual desire was often censored and seen as obscene, immoral, and shocking. As I intend to show, the sexual frankness that Tóibín’s main character displays in the earlier version of *The South* was unacceptable at the time, and this can be one of the reasons why so many publishers rejected the novel.

Key words. Colm Tóibín; (self) censorship; sexuality; Ireland; *The South*

(p. 377) Colm Tóibín’s *The South* (1990) tells the story of Katherine Proctor, an Irish wife and mother who escapes home to start a new life in 1950s Spain, where she reinvents herself as an artist and falls in love with another man, discovering the sexual passion that her marriage lacked. *The South* marks the beginning of Tóibín’s literary career; until then, he had been a well-known public intellectual who “had acquired a reputation as one of the brightest and sharpest pens in Ireland’s new critical journalism” (Böss 24). In the wake of the novel’s publication, a majority of reviewers enthusiastically welcomed Tóibín’s literary debut, seeing him as a “promising young writer” (Sanderson), who managed to produce “a masterful first novel” (Ryerson). Barbara Probst Solomon also admires the narrative’s “haunting quality,” but she then observes: “Yes, of course, women do abandon their children—but it is the apparent lack of conflict about it there that creates an unreal note.” A similar impression was shared by many other early reviewers, who either remarked on the moral make-up of Katherine or who regarded her as a female character that breaks the principles of verisimilitude.¹ Apparently, a considerable

¹ The Irish reviewer Mary Leland comments that “it is not altogether easy to accept that [Katherine] would have left her ten-year-old son with the unapologetic alacrity suggested here” (1990). Writing for *The Irish Times*, Aisling Maguire takes the view that Katherine is a “self-regarding paranoid” (1990). June Considine opines that Katherine’s “decision to leave her son and her subsequent lack of any believable guilt is difficult to comprehend—especially as the book is set in the very moralistic and unliberated ’50s” (1990). In 1991, *The South* was

number of readers disliked the novel's protagonist, and Tóibín became aware of this fact. In an interview for the Irish Times, the author responded to this type of criticism by saying, "I never wanted her to be good [...] and I'm surprised to find that that seems to upset people. Why? Why should characters in fiction have to be good, or have to be sympathetic?" (Wallace). These moral judgments on Tóibín's central character come as no surprise. After all, the novel centers on the personal fulfillment of a woman who rebels against gender expectations and a deeply entrenched ideology of domesticity.

Tóibín soon obtained recognition as an outstanding author when *The South* was awarded the prestigious Irish Times-Aer Lingus First Novel Prize in 1991. Although he is one of the most prominent literary voices in Ireland today, Tóibín had to face enormous difficulties in having *The South* published. Between 1986 and 1989, *The South* was "turned down by most English publishers" (Canning 170). In a 1987 letter sent by Imogen Parker, the literary agent informs Tóibín that Secker did not accept the manuscript, as they found it "too insubstantial" [MS 44,495 /4]. Another publishing house, (p. 378) Macmillan, simply said that "they did not want to do the book," but that if Tóibín "wrote anything else, they would like see it" (Hyland).

Though *The South* was being rejected by many publishers, Tóibín had received the support of two authors he admires: "Both John McGahern and John Banville had read [*The South*] and they said it was ok [...] Since they were the two people I was reading, I took that very seriously" (Hyland). Tóibín relates in another interview that "by the time [*The South*] was accepted by Serpent's Tail, twenty publishers had turned it down" (Canning 178). Founded in 1986, Serpent's Tail became part of the counter-culture rhetoric of Thatcherist England, with publishers who "fed and stoked an appetite for [...] 'transgressive' writing" (Tonkin). As a politically incorrect novel for its time, *The South* can certainly count as a clear representative of the "transgressive" writing that Serpent's Tail was promoting.

In this article, I will look at the drafts of *The South*—on file in a special collection of the National Library of Ireland—and argue that, for the novel to be published, Tóibín softened Katherine's characterization as an "abject" mother and sanitized the language of her sexual feelings. Although in the published version there are a number of explicit sexual scenes, Katherine's most passionate emotions and her desire for her Spanish lover, Miguel, were virtually edited out in the revision process. Interestingly, the type of sexual subjectivity that was elided in the revisions of *The South* reemerges in Tóibín's later work, with gay characters who openly express their desire for their lovers' body.² As will be

published in the United States. American reviewer Judith Dunford admires Tóibín's novel but sees the protagonist as "selfish, angry, self-absorbed, casually cruel" (1991). Corinna Lothar contends that "Katherine is so totally self-absorbed, that it is difficult for the reader to be moved by her sorrows, or her search of freedom and self-determination" (1991). Another reviewer, Peter Finn, regards the protagonist's lack of guilt as a narrative flaw, since "we never see her grieve just as she never truly examines her decision to leave her first child" (1991).

² This is the case, for example, of his first gay novel *The Story of the Night* (1996) and some of his gay short stories, such as "The Pearl Fishers" and "Barcelona, 1975" (both in *The Empty Family*, 2010).

argued, The South's publishing problems and its revision process reflect the conservative political culture of the 1980s and early 1990s.

This study will consider Tóibín's *The South* within the larger context of an Irish culture of silence, repression, and censorship with regard to the body and sexuality. Until recently, a sexual morality of prudery and chastity prevailed in Ireland, a fact that sociologist Tom Inglis attributes to the traditional central role of the Catholic Church in the Irish society: "Much of what was written and spoken about sexuality in Ireland during the nineteen and twentieth centuries was dominated by the teachings and ethos of the Catholic Church" (17). In a confessional state such as Ireland, Catholic teachings on the body and sexuality have had a strong influence on the psychology of individuals, perpetuating social attitudes of guilt and secrecy surrounding sexual desire (Inglis 249). Until as late as the 1990s, those who did not conform to the norms of sexual respectability were often shamed, punished, or confined to state-run institutions, such as the infamous Magdalene laundries for unmarried mothers (see Smith).

This sexual morality had also a devastating effect on the lives of homosexuals, who often became the recipients of intimidation, rejection, and legal discrimination. Because same-sex desire was viewed as utterly wrong and pathological, many gay men like Tóibín felt profoundly disturbed about their own sexuality. As the writer notes: "I remember being a certain age, like 17, when someone described to me what two guys did together and being absolutely horrified that this could occur, while at the same time [...] longed to do the same. How could you manage that?" (Morton).

In his early twenties, Tóibín moved to Barcelona and lived there from 1975 until 1978, enjoying the vibrant cultural life of the Catalan capital in the demise of Franco's dictatorship. As a gay man, Tóibín achieved in Spain a kind of freedom that had been unavailable to him in Ireland.³ The writer frequently refers to his three years in Catalonia as a time of great personal maturation, naming "[his] going to Spain: [his] homosexuality" as one of the primary influences in his writing (D'Erasmó 166). Interestingly, as Eibhear Walshe remarks, the sense of excitement and reinvention that Tóibín enjoyed in Catalonia "is also experienced by Katherine Proctor [in *The South*], and Barcelona offered for Tóibín, as it does for Katherine, a chance of an aesthetic, political and sexual redefinition as part of the journey away from Ireland" (24).

In the 1980s, Toibín returned to Dublin to work as a journalist who expressed "the voice of the young, urban, anti-establishment Ireland" (Böss 24). He was the editor of *Magill*—a news magazine—from 1982 to 1985, at a time when the state imposed a strict censorship on the press. In 1983, Tóibín and his team won a Supreme Court victory, "enabling them to publish a story about the prostitution underworld, after a pimp burned to death a former prostitute and her mother in revenge (p. 379) for leaving him" (Ferriter 714). Thus journalists such as Tóibín helped raise awareness about sexual realities that had been hidden from public opinion until then. Marjorie Howes outlines that, for the first

³ See Tóibín, 2000: 243–45

time, cases involving teenage pregnancy, infanticide, and abortion were highly publicized: “Sexuality in Ireland became more hotly debated and more openly debated than ever before” (930). As a result of all these public debates, the ethics surrounding sexuality became a recurrent topic of conflict and dissent in 1980s Ireland.

In the 1990s, Tóibín continued writing newspaper articles against discrimination based on sexual behavior, proclaiming that “it is really important for the health of our society and its citizens that the fear and guilt surrounding sexuality be removed” (“The Thin Gay Line”). Though not openly gay in the early 1990s, Tóibín wrote an open letter to Health Minister John O’Connell, urging him to remove the Victorian law against gay men:

At the moment a woman can go to bed with another woman and anything they do, as consenting adults, is their own business. So too a man and a woman can go to bed without the police having any right to come into their bedroom and arrest them. But two men cannot do this. This is absurd. (“Dear Dr. O’Connell”)

Tóibín openly denounces here the clash between politics, public morality, and individual rights. In the case of gay men, Diarmaid Ferriter notes that “the laws relating to homosexuality were draconian, and dated from 1861” (715). Male homosexuality was not decriminalized in Ireland until 1993, and this decriminalization was established through the deletion of a law penalizing anal intercourse.⁴

Throughout the 1980s and early 1990s, issues connected to sex and sexuality attained a wider relevance in public debates about social change and individual freedom. In those years, the state’s administration of censorship still focused on matters of sex, with a paternalistic concern to “protect” people from “immoral” behavior and liberal tendencies. As Howes indicates, Irish censorship “was about sexuality more than anything else,” as “the initial draft of the 1929 Censorship of Publication Act equated sexual passion with sexual immorality” (928, 929). Sexual desire was, in fact, censored and was regarded as obscene. In one of his scholarly articles, Irish author John Banville highlights that “as recently as 1987, the Censorship Board banned Alex Comfort’s *The Joy of Sex* and, a much more serious matter, Philip Rawson’s *The Erotic Art of India*, a scholarly study” (148). In the course of the 1990s, censorship laws changed rapidly; a popular magazine, *Playboy*, was unbanned in 1996, and “it quickly became Ireland’s highest selling men’s magazine” (Hayes).

Although Tóibín’s *The South* was not banned by the Censorship Board in Ireland, the novel easily could have encountered the opposition of censorship had the sexual content of the drafts remained intact. Even after all the modifications for the final version, *The South* still remained a subversive text because of its sexual scenes. Irish journalist Jonathan Philibin Bowman explains how, several weeks before *The South* came out in Ireland, the liberal newspaper *Sunday Independent* published an extract of it, with “a

⁴ The law that was removed in 1993 reads as follows: “Whosoever shall be convicted of the abominable crime of buggery, committed either with mankind or with any animal, shall be liable [...] to be kept in penal servitude” (Ferriter 715).

whole load of paragraphs that the paper didn't print. Mostly to do with sex" (54). As this anecdote reveals, Tóibín's *The South* was seen to defy Ireland's culture of prudery with regard to the body and sexuality.

When Tóibín finished *The South* in 1986, he already knew that "he was breaking all the rules" and that people would find it "strange for a first novel" (Vezzani 130, 133). Being such a "strange" novel, *The South* was not welcomed in its original form. The writer acknowledges that:

The South was really worked on. A lot was added at a late stage, and lot left out. I had a very good editor at Serpent's Tail called Marsha Rowe [...] I learnt a lot from her. (Canning 179)

At this point, I should emphasize that I do not contend here that Rowe was responsible for the modifications that I address in this article, since the manuscript presumably underwent numerous revisions and rewrites before it was submitted to Serpent's Tail. Tóibín himself admitted in 1990 that *The South* "has been in many forms and it's been changed many times," lamenting that "there are beautiful chapters of it that no one will ever see" (Bowman 52). Many of the "emendations" on the drafts cannot be considered mere stylistic changes. In this analysis, I shall demonstrate that, whereas (p. 380) the published version softens but preserves the protagonist's characterization as an "abject" mother, the modifications on the manuscript served to lessen the references to Katherine's sexual agency and subjectivity, thus reducing the subversive potential of this novel at a time when sexual desire was often seen as shocking and immoral. Additionally, I will argue that, in its treatment of sexuality, there is a stronger sense of a gay subtext in the pre-published version of *The South*.

As indicated in the opening paragraph, Tóibín's *The South* surprised many of its readers on its publication because the protagonist, Katherine, comes across as "downright unlikeable specifically as a mother" (Costello-Sullivan 40, emphasis in the original). In the earlier version, Katherine is an even more "unlikeable" mother, and this becomes particularly true in connection to her daughter in Spain, Isona. A dissident of Franco's regime, Miguel—Katherine's partner and Isona's father—is captured and tortured by the police, and this experience makes him develop severe psychological disorders. Some months after, Katherine begins to suspect that Miguel has taken a sexual interest in Isona, noticing that he "had fixed on her in some way" (151). In the 1990 text, readers are not given enough clues to judge, except for a reference to a "game" that Miguel plays in the wood with his child:

'El Papa em porta al bosc,' she said [...] 'And what are you going to do in the wood?' Katherine asked her. *'El Papa em conta histories,'* the child said. 'Which stories?' Katherine asked. *'La historia del llop que viu al bosc.'* Miguel heard and turned around and growled. It was a game. Katherine watched him with relief. Maybe he was getting better [...] Isona ran to her mother as though she were afraid and when Katherine took her up in her arms she laughed. (143–44)

Here, Katherine's suspicions are momentarily dispelled; she is relieved because she now feels that Isona is safe with Miguel in the wood. This is not the scenario that the manuscript portrays:

... Miquel heard [Isona] saying this and turned around and growled at her. He grinned. As though she was afraid, Isona ran to her mother who took her up in her arms. [MS 44, 463/6]

Significantly, the same episode in the draft acquires a grimmer tone due to the child's panicky reaction when Miguel growls and then grins at her. Whereas in the published text Tóibín has Isona laugh, in the draft he portrays this scene as a revelatory instance of the child's suffering. Significantly, contrary to the 1990 version, in the draft Katherine is unambiguously aware of Isona's vulnerability, but she does not protect her from Miguel because she is convinced that "the child is what is keeping him from falling apart" and that "if she kept Isona away from him she herself would have nothing left to do with him, they would have to separate" [MS 44, 463/6]. Therefore, in his earlier text Tóibín makes it clear that what preoccupies Katherine is not the wellbeing of her daughter, but her relationship with Miguel. In both texts of *The South*, Tóibín depicts Katherine as a callous and neglectful mother, but in the manuscript he further insists on her lack of maternal love for Isona.

In both the 1986 and 1990 versions, Katherine's unheroic behavior leads to tragedy when Miguel abducts Isona, killing himself and his daughter in a car accident. In the draft, this accident is preceded by another event: Miguel's attempt to murder Katherine when he assaults her as she walks home at night:

She heard something move behind her. As she turned she felt a hand grip her shoulder hard and then another hand grab under her arm with its fingers on her breast [...] She felt [Miguel's] body pushing against her, forcing her towards the edge of the roadway [...] At some places there was an incline down to the valley. At other parts the drop was sheer. [MS 44,463 /6]

When Miguel releases and pushes her, Katherine falls on to a soft surface and survives the attack. This episode was deleted in the revision process, and this elision may be connected with the social sensibilities of the time and the traditional silencing of gender violence. In his draft, Tóibín was dealing with unpalatable matters of domestic violence and abuse by depicting Miguel's incestuous desire for Isona and his attempt to kill Katherine. Arguably, just as Katherine's "abject" motherhood had to be softened for the final version of *The South*, this picture of family dysfunction was similarly modified in the revision process to make the novel more acceptable for a general public.

(p. 381) As I have been discussing, in *The South* Tóibín not only debunks the ideals of motherhood and the family, but he also breaks the taboos of sexual desire. According to Roberta Geftter Wondrich, *The South* pays tribute to the sexually liberating power attached to expatriation: "The protagonist leaves behind her former paralysed, eerily preserved body and sexuality, almost as an old skin to slough off, and is ready to embrace a renewed, deep eroticism with the stranger, Miguel" (10). This vision of expatriation as a chance for sexual freedom resonates in Tóibín's semi-autobiographical short-story

“Barcelona, 1975” (2010a), where a young Irish man enjoys the “excitement of being in a foreign city alone,” as he soon finds the pleasure of “soft warm skin and sex” (145, 147).

Considering Barcelona’s personal significance for Tóibín, it is no coincidence that the social life of the city features more prominently in the original version of *The South*. One example concerns the quarter where Michael Graves, Katherine’s Irish friend in Barcelona, lives:

He lived in a pension in the Barrio Chino: the small area off the Ramblas made up of dingy, grubby streets where men hung around waiting for prostitutes. It was cheap, he said, and he enjoyed the atmosphere. [MS 44,463 /5]

He lived in a pensión in the Barrio Chino. It was cheap, he said, and he enjoyed the atmosphere. (55)

The line describing the Barrio Chino disappears in the revision process, and, consequently, the underworld of prostitution is omitted. With this omission, the published text also eliminates this character’s morally challenging appreciation of the Barrio Chino as a good place to live and enjoy life, surrounded by prostitutes. Tóibín’s attempt to picture Barcelona’s red-light district in *The South* was not devoid of political connotations, given the sexual morality of 1980s Ireland and the silencing of prostitution.

Thus the city’s social atmosphere is given much more prominence in the earlier version. In a chapter that was edited out, Tóibín has Katherine describing her impressions of 1980s Barcelona:

The girls went to the Ramblas to buy books; all of the books they bought, when unwrapped, turned out to be about sex, including a book in Catalan on how to make love to a woman as well as a novel in a new pornographic series in Spanish. No one giggled or laughed about the books on sex. They passed them from one to the other, showing significant passages. [MS 44,463 /2]

Here, Katherine perceives how these young Spanish women publicly display an attitude toward sex that would have been unimaginable in 1980s Ireland. These young women do not regard sexual desire as a sinful and shameful secret, but they see it rather as a natural and joyous experience about which they speak freely. Tóibín’s portrayal of these books on sex is not an innocent act either; these young women are reading published material that would have been censored in 1980s Ireland.

As a painter, the Katherine of the drafts is well aware of the subversive potential of sexuality and the body as a subject in art. The 1986 version contains a chapter in which a journalist interviews a sixty-four-year-old Katherine, who, in one of her 1960s Dublin exhibitions, courageously displayed “some nude paintings of men” [MS 44,463/2]. As the interview progresses, we also discover that she is working on a series of self-portraits: “I have done some nudes of myself. I used a mirror for those. Sounds horrible, doesn’t it? But if men can do it, why can’t women?” [MS 44,463/2]. As illustrated here, Tóibín’s original intention was for Katherine to emerge as a bohemian painter who challenges both

the predominant culture of prudery and the masculinist conventions in the world of art. This is one characteristic of the protagonist that was lost in the revision process, as the Katherine of the published text devotes herself only to painting landscapes.

Originally, too, Tóibín created Katherine as a more self-assured and active woman. Unlike the Katherine of the 1990 text, in the draft the protagonist shows her sexual attraction to Miguel when she first sees him standing at the bar: she admires his jet-black eyes, perfect teeth, wide mouth, and slightly long hair. As he leaves, she has her eyes on him: “When I looked again he was walking out the door. He turned and glanced back for a moment and grinned when he found that I was watching” [MS 44,463 /4]. This is not the scenario that Tóibín recreates in the published version, where it is Miguel who initiates the flirtation. Their second encounter begins in a different way in each text: **(p. 382)**

As I was led down by the waiter, I saw him and he fixed his eyes on me. [MS 44,463 /4]
As the waiter led me down to a vacant table, I saw him fix his eyes on me. (17)

Curiously, while in the 1990 text Katherine finds Miguel staring at her, in the manuscript she observes him in order to draw his attention to her. This is a relevant distinction, since in his revisions Tóibín modified Katherine’s behavior toward Miguel to make her fit into the stereotype of female passivity.

This passivity of the Katherine of the 1990 text also extends to her sexual relationship with Miguel. The published novel does not omit the sexual scenes between the two, but this revised text hardly conveys Katherine’s sexual subjectivity and her lust for Miguel’s body. As a result, part of the erotic charge of the 1986 draft disappears in the revision process. To illustrate this point, we may compare the following passages:

He took off his jacket and shirt and she could see the outline of his penis through his cord trousers. [MS 44,463 /5]
He took off his jacket and shirt and when he was naked he came over and put his arms around her and she could feel his heart beating fast. (27)

While the published text simply shows a naked Miguel, in the draft Miguel’s body is seen through Katherine’s eyes. Moreover, in the earlier version Katherine has her own agency and deliberately looks at the outline of Miguel’s erect penis, the suggestion being that she finds it exciting and sexually enticing. The next two quotations further reinforce the claim that the published text reduces Katherine’s sexual subjectivity and agency:

He stood up and stretched and she lay back and watched him: his straight thin white back, the rough hair on his legs and the soft dark hair on his bottom. He went out to the toilet and when he came back she looked at his penis. [MS 44,463 /5]
When he stood up and stretched she lay back and watched him: his straight, thin white back and the rough hair on his legs. He was cold when he came back from the toilet and they huddled against one another in bed, shuddering at the cold. (23)

This scene occurs when they wake up in bed, after having spent the night together. Miguel sleeps naked, so Katherine observes the whole of his body when he gets up. In both cases, this moment leads to another sexual relationship, but in the manuscript there is a stronger sense that Katherine looks at Miguel showing sexual intent. Similarly, Katherine's sexual pleasure is more clearly revealed in the manuscript, as the following quotations show:

She was still coming when he started to ejaculate and they held it for as long as they could. [MS 44,463 /5]

He started to ejaculate and together they held it for as long as they could. (27)

As is obvious here, Katherine's body disappears at the moment of sexual climax, whereas Miguel's does not. Tóibín's decision to diminish Katherine's sexual subjectivity and agency raises questions as to the traditional silencing of women's sexuality in patriarchal societies, together with the writer's need to make *The South* a more "publishable" novel. What is also true is that, stereotypically, sexual agency and assertiveness have been considered to be masculine traits, so Tóibín may have chosen to "feminize" his protagonist by turning her into Miguel's passive lover, thus hindering any possible readings of Katherine as a "disguised" gay man. All in all, although the published version of *The South* remains a narrative about sexual liberation, Katherine's passionate desire for Miguel was virtually edited out in the revision process.

Independently of her sexual desires, Katherine's observations of Miguel's body are consistently reduced in other scenes where no sex is involved. When Miguel returns home after being tortured, Katherine notices:

He was wearing his underpants and shirt in bed and when he got out to go downstairs she noticed that there were marks on the back of his legs. She called him back and when she looked carefully she saw that there were deep red marks like rings all down his two legs. She made him take off his underpants and he winced with pain when she touched the raw welts on his bottom. [MS 44,463/5]

(p. 383) When he got out of bed to go downstairs she noticed bruises and cuts on his back. She called him then and asked him what had happened. He returned and lay down again, and told her that they had hit him, but not much. (84)

As is evident, the revised text shows a much more concise and distant description of this moment, and Katherine's agency once again disappears when it comes to her most intimate interactions with Miguel—"she made him take off his underpants," we read in the earlier version. Furthermore, whereas the published text merely informs us about Miguel's injuries, the manuscript deals with the violence inflicted on his body, evoking the disturbing image of policemen brutalizing Miguel by whipping his bottom.

Miguel's bottom is precisely one part of his body that is never mentioned in the published novel. This is hardly surprising because in the final version Katherine does not eroticize Miguel's body as much as she does in the 1986 text. However, it is also true that, at the time Tóibín wrote his novel, the desire for a man's bottom was culturally associated

with gay sexuality—for instance, in 1993 the legal acceptance of gay sexuality in Ireland was equated with the deletion of a law against anal intercourse. Though I cannot claim that Tóibín omitted the references to Miguel’s bottom to suppress covert allusions to homosexuality, I do suggest here that there is a stronger sense of a gay subtext in the earlier version of *The South*. This gay subtext, I argue, runs parallel to the more obvious story of an unconventional Irish wife/mother in flight from the constraints of patriarchal Ireland.

Just like the writer himself when he first came to Spain, Katherine becomes sexually adventurous far from a repressive Ireland. One of the edited-out chapters describes a passionate affair that Katherine has with a stranger in Lourdes,⁵ Southern France. Just as she arrives at the hotel, she perceives how one of the waiters “had cast his eyes over her body,” doing it “openly, almost casually” [MS 44,464/2]. A flattered Katherine returns his advances, and, later, when he brings her dinner to her room, she invites him in and they end up having ardent sex: “His tongue on her breasts, licking them, his teeth gently biting at her nipples. His whole head between her legs, his tongue working at her, working at her over and over” [MS 44,464/2]. The following day at breakfast, Katherine “watched him move around the tables,” and then “stayed in bed most afternoon, naked, waiting for him, thinking about him” [MS 44,464/2]. In their subsequent encounters, Katherine performs oral sex on her unnamed lover—“she held it in her hands and pulled it back towards her tongue and licked it”—and engages in anal intercourse with—“she could feel his hard penis pushing against her bottom until it entered her there” [MS 44,464/2]. Being her first time, the experience turns out to be painful: “She gasped each time he came back in [...] She wanted him to end” [MS 44,464/2]. It goes without saying that the published novel features no such types of sexual practices, and that Miguel remains Katherine’s only sexual lover, apart from her deserted husband. Understandably, anal intercourse, which was linked to gay sexuality, is not even hinted at in the final version of *The South*.

Inevitably, all the modifications to the manuscript also affected the narrative style of *The South*. In his introduction to the 2015 Picador Classic edition of Tóibín’s first novel, Roy Foster writes that “Katherine sees things rather than feels them” (viii). This is precisely so, in part, because Tóibín, after all his revisions, created a distance between the reader and Katherine’s emotions. To make this clear, I would like to return to the episode in which Miguel suffers his mental breakdown. In the 1990 version, Katherine considers escaping from him, but her descriptions of their deteriorated domestic life transmit almost no emotion. About their sexual relationships, she now relates: “Always he wanted to be finished quickly and, being an expert in all things physical, in lighting fires, chopping wood, stretching canvas, he knew how to reach orgasm quickly. He no longer cared whether she did or not” (143). It is only when she privately speaks with her friend Michael

⁵ Lourdes is a major site of pilgrimage for Catholics due its Marian apparitions in the nineteenth century. Ironically, in the draft of *The South* Lourdes becomes the place where Katherine begins her sexual liberation away from the sexual morality of Catholic Ireland.

Graves that her angst becomes more apparent, as she confesses that she has been afraid and that “things have just fallen apart” (149).

On the contrary, in the 1986 text Tóibín highlights Katherine’s anger and bitterness about Miguel’s lack of affection for her, now that he is suffering acute mental disorders: “Everything else had gone. Except the urges. The urge to eat and the urge to fuck. He had always been part human, (p. 384) part appetite” [MS 44,463 /6]. Katherine does have her own reasons to be afraid of Miguel, who, all of a sudden, became sexually aggressive, selfish, and malevolent. When they make love, she perceives “how the glare of his eyes intensified and darkened” [MS 44,463 /6]. In one of the scenes, a troubled Katherine looks at herself in the mirror, seeing herself as:

The naked woman with the sound going through her head all day. You fuck me. You fuck me.
You fuck me. You fuck me. You fuck me like I was a dog. [MS 44,463 /6]

Obviously, this emotionally turbulent scene does not feature in the 1990 text, where Tóibín clearly sanitizes the language of Katherine’s sexual feelings.⁶ Needless to say, the image of Katherine being penetrated as if she were a dog is a highly transgressive one for its time, as it denotes both sexual violence and can even hint at anal intercourse, with all its connotations of “depravity” and gay sexuality. Unsurprisingly, the directness and explicitness of the 1986 version become replaced by a more detached and “polite” language in the published text: “She took off her clothes and stood there in the candlelight looking at herself in the mirror: a naked woman in a dim candlelit room; a naked woman of more than forty” (142). Ultimately, as I have been discussing, the modifications on 1986 text not only reduce the novel’s subversive potential, but also influence its narrative style, as the Katherine of the final version emerges as a character who, in the words of Roy Foster, remains “*strangely distanced*” (viii; my emphasis). This is partly the case because, as I have explained throughout this study, Katherine’s sexual subjectivity becomes substantially reduced in the revision process.

To conclude, I would like to underline that, when he was writing *The South*, Tóibín was aware that he was breaking the cultural norms of 1980s Ireland, a society where Catholic values on family life, domesticity, and sexuality still held sway.⁷ In fact, because the protagonist represents a blatant reversal of the cultural expectations of motherhood, many readers regarded Katherine as an unlikeable or “unreal” female character. As has been noted here, in the drafts Katherine emerges as an even more callous mother who, contrary to the 1990 text, is clearly aware of her daughter’s suffering at the hands of Miguel. Presumably, in his revisions Tóibín softened Katherine’s “unmotherly” behavior to make his novel more acceptable to a general public. Thus if the published novel elicited

⁶ There is a second copy of this draft where these lines are crossed out, which may indicate that Tóibín self-edited the chapter before sending the manuscript to Serpent’s Tail [MS 44,463 /6]

⁷ It was not until 1995, for example, that divorce became legal in Ireland, and this legalization saw “wild claims as to the demise of the family” (Conroy 76).

negative comments on Katherine's role as an "abject" mother, the earlier version would have attracted a more emphatic response in that respect.

On numerous occasions, Tóibín has related how he grew up at a time when homosexuality "was not allowed for as a possibility" (2001: 275), a fact that marked him as a gay man: "My sexuality [...] was something about which part of me remained uneasy, timid and melancholy" (2001: 2). Crucial to Tóibín's subjectivity as a gay man was his time in Barcelona in the 1970s. In fact, one of the traits that the writer himself and his character, Katherine, share is their experiences of sexual frustration in Ireland and sexual liberation in Spain. As a journalist in Dublin in the 1980s, Tóibín became vocal about issues related to discrimination based on sexual behavior. However, his own homosexuality—being a crime until 1993—became a topic that he could not address publicly, so Tóibín turned to literary writing as means of "reaching inwards" and "going home to a part of [himself] that felt closer" (Canning 174). Furthermore, I would also add that, by "inhabiting Katherine" (Canning 174), Tóibín was enacting a type of "personal rebellion" against the sexual morality that had made him suffer as a gay man. Precisely, the topic of sexual liberation takes a more central stage in the manuscript, which shows a stronger sense of a gay subtext in its treatment of sexuality.

Central to this essay has been the idea that, when Tóibín wrote *The South* in the 1980s, sexual desire—if directly addressed—was often censored and seen as offensive, immoral, and shocking. Consequently, the sexual frankness that Katherine displays in the drafts was unacceptable for its time. Had not Tóibín's language been altered specifically in connection to sex and sexuality, *The South* easily would have encountered the opposition of censorship on its publication. Seemingly, to make *The South* a more publishable text, Tóibín not only sanitized the language of his protagonist's sexual feelings, but he also modified her sexual behavior to make her fit into the stereotype of female passivity, thus reducing the subversive potential of the novel. Moreover, the type of sexual subjectivity that was elided in the revision process re-emerges in some of his later fictions, with gay (p. 385) characters who openly express their sexual desires for other men. Nonetheless, in spite of the aforementioned changes on the drafts of *The South*, Tóibín's first novel remains a transgressive narrative in its own right, defying the restrictive culture of sexuality and domesticity that was prevalent at the time it was published.

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